

CHEMICAL RESPONSES OF JUJUBE TREE, *ZIZIPHUS* SPP. TO FLAT-HEADED BORERS *CHRYSOBOTHRIS. AFFINIS* (FABRICIUS, 1794) INFESTATION

Mohammed M. Alderawii and Aqeel Alyousuf *

Department of Plant Protection, College of Agriculture, University of Basrah, Iraq

*Email: Aqeel.alyousof@okstate.edu

Abstract

Jujube trees are infested by flat-headed borers (*Chrysobothris affinis* (Fabricius, 1974) (Coleoptera, Buprestidae) in Province of Basra; the result of the field survey during the growing season of 2021/2022 indicated that the highest infestation of flat-headed borers was on the cv. Tuffahi, with an average rate of 61.06%, followed the Bambawi and Ziatooni cultivars, reaching 18.51 and 18.45%, respectively. While, the lowest infestation was 9.95% on cultivar Wild. However, the highest infestation rates of the borers were recorded at in Zubair and Safwan regions; while the lowest infestation were at Madinah and Imam Al-Sadiq regions. The susceptibility of cultivars to infestation of flat-headed borers was studied through the chemical analysis of phenols in the trunks of different jujube cultivars. The study showed the presence of 15 phenolic compounds in the trunks of the different cultivars; there is negative relationship ($r = -0.97$ and -0.93) between the infestation rate and the concentration of rutin and gallic compounds. In order to figure out the reason for the occurrence of the infestation in the old branches (two years and above) compared to the young branches, which are not infested with the borers; the moisture content in the branches was studied, and an negative relationship was found between the moisture content and the insect infestation rate; high moisture content was found in the young branches, which reached 52.59% compared to the two-year-old branches that contained 30.90% moisture. The infestation flat-headed borers reduced the percentage of proteins, carbohydrates and the content of chlorophyll in the leaves of the infested trees; their averages were 15.09, 58.32% and 1.82 g/100 gm in leaves, respectively, compared to 18.92 and 71.78%, 4.22 g/100 g. in the non-infested trees; While the study indicated an increase of the concentration of phenols in leaves of infested trees, with an average of 9.78%, compared to leaves in healthy trees, which averaged 9.45% of phenols. Finally, Jujube trees have a set of integrated defense systems against pests that attack the bark and wood that may be one of the IPM elements preventing borers infestation on Jujube plantation.

Keywords: Buprestidae, *Chrysobothris. Affinis*, Flatheaded Borers, Jujube, phenols

INTRODUCTION

Jujube tree, *Ziziphus* spp. (Rhamnaceae), is one of the evergreen fruit trees that grow in tropical, subtropical and warm temperate regions (San and Yildirim, 2010, Williams, 2006); In Iraq, the cultivation of commercial cultivars Twofahi (*Z. mauritiana*) has been increased mainly due to the economic importance of this cultivar and the great economic return to farmer; the number of Jujube trees is around 146,720 trees on an area of 5,675 Iraqi dunams (Department of Horticulture-Barsa, Ministry of Agriculture, 2021; (Altaha et al., 2006). In Basra, Jujube trees are infested by several pests that cause economic damage to these trees. However, Recently, Flat-headed Borers

Chrysobothris affinis (Fabricius, 1794) (Buprestidae: Coleoptera) have been recorded infesting Jujube trees in the commercial jujube orchards throughout the Province, causing a significant economic damage. The infestation ratio varied among the jujube cultivars; the highest rate was on the cultivar Twofahi, however, the lowest rate was recorded in the wild cultivar (Alderawii and Alyousuf, 2022). Neonicotinoid insecticides were applied to control Flat-headed borers enhancing the production, with average of 60.10 and 60.00 kg / tree, respectively, compared to 39.50 kg of the check trees. (Alderawii and Alyousuf, in publishing).

Flat-headed borers (Buprestidae) are widespread in North America and attack fruit trees, shade and ornamental trees; they cause great economic losses in trees, that are difficult to control; the infestation of borers are considered one of the most important problems in commercial nurseries and landscaping; it can cause a rapid decline in the families of economically important plants in the severe infestation (Wellso and Manley, 2007, Adkins et al., 2010).

Host-plant resistance HPR can be involved in plant defense against the herbivores through various mechanisms, antibiosis, antixenosis, and or tolerance (Painter, 1951). HPR can affect the insects by causing the host plant unfavorable for feeding or ovipositing or by existing toxic properties that harmfully affect the herbivores' performance, which maximizes the development time, causes mortality of the herbivores and reduce the herbivores' mass (Mitchell et al., 2016, Hill et al., 2012). In fact, the chemical defenses vary in the plants, so that can be involved against a wide range of the pests; the non-protein chemicals such as phenols, alkaloids and resins, which have strong effects on the herbivores, have the ability to act more quickly than protein-chemicals defenses (Martin et al., 2002, Christiansen et al., 1999); phenolic compounds, which are present in several forms in plants, are the most important of these chemical defenses; some of the phenolic compounds produced by the plant as a result of the infestation of the pests; the induced phenols are more toxic or more specific to the invading organism than the phenols found within the metabolic compounds naturally (Bonello et al., 2003).

Many Biochemical characteristics involved in the plant resistance have been studied in many trees; for example, several volatiles related to plant-insect interactions have been identified that include the apricot trees and flat headed borer *Capnodis tenebrionis* (Buprestidae) (Bari et al., 2019). A preliminary finding on the chemical ecology of *A. biguttatus* which infesting by native oak trees revealed to the role of the bioactive VOCs of the phloem in host-finding for this forest insect (Vuts et al., 2016). (Villari et al., 2016) found Manchurian ash *Fraxinus mandshurica* trees were less preferable to emerald ash borers *Agrilus planipennis* (Buprestidae) adult feeding and laying eggs than susceptible host plants, more resistant to larval feeding; their resistance is attributed to the higher levels of bark lignan, coumarin, proline, tyramine, and defense-proteins. Resistant cultivars, which are developed through traditional breeding methods or genetic engineering, is an essential part of integrated pest management programs (Maher et al., 2018). This study aimed to assess the insect-host plant interaction of flat-headed borers infesting Jujube orchards.

Materials and methods

Infestation rates of flat-headed borers on different cultivars of Jujube trees.

A survey of flat-headed borers (*C. affinis*) infesting different cultivars of Jujube trees (Tuffahi, Zaitooni Bambawi, and wild) in Basra Province during growing season of 2021/2022. The infestation rates of flat-headed borers were recorded in each Jujube orchard. The infestation rate (equation 1) of the pest was determined based on the symptoms of infestation on the trees (the presence of holes, dead branches, the presence of traces and feeding tunnels for larvae and gummy secretions), as well as cutting the branches that have symptoms and dissecting them and noting the presence of larvae inside the branches.

$$\text{Infestation rate} = \frac{\text{The number of infested trees}}{\text{Total number of trees}} \times 100 \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Detection of biochemical traits for Plant Defense

Determination of phenols of the trunk phloem

The phenol content of trunk phloem of Jujube cultivars was estimated in the laboratories of the Ministry of Science and Technology, according to the following method:

- 1) 100 g of sun-dried branches of each cultivar was ground well; 5 g of each sample was taken and soaked with 60 ml HCL (2N) with a ratio of 1: 12 (W: V) respectively in a conical flask; the mixture was placed in a water bath at 100°C for 45 minutes.
- 2) The sample was filtered with a 0.45 Millipore filter; the sample was extracted four times with 25 ml petroleum ether (40 - 60 / each time) for removal of carotene and chlorophyll by using a separating funnel.
- 3) The sample was extracted four times with 25 ml of ethyl acetate each time for extracting the flavonoids.
- 4) The ethyl acetate layer was separated from the aqueous part using a separating funnel and passed through anhydrous sodium sulfate for removing the moisture.
- 5) The sample was heated on a water bath to remove the solvent, then the filtration process was carried out again with 0.45 Millipore filter.
- 6) The sample was injected HPLC device (Sykam, German (model of 2013)).

Determination of Moisture content of Jujube branches

The branches of one and two years Jujube cultivars were weighed using a sensitive digital scale (Mettler PS30 type with digital screen, German); then, the same samples were dried using an electric oven (Binder, German) at a temperature of 70 °C for three days (72 hours); next, it was weighed again to estimate the moisture content according to the following equation.

$$\% \text{ moisture} = \frac{\text{the green weight} - \text{the oven dry weight}}{\text{the oven dry weight}} \times 100 \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Study of chemical responses of Jujube cultivars to flat-headed borer's infestation

Determination of protein content of Jujube leaves

The protein content of leaves of infested and non-infested Jujube cultivars were estimated in the laboratories of the College of Agriculture / University of Basrah. The leaves were collected, washed and dried by using an electric oven at a temperature of 70 °C for 72 hours, the leaves were ground well using a blender. The protein content was estimated according to the following method of (Cresser and Parsons, 1979):

- 1) 0.2 gm of dry and ground leaf sample was placed in a 100-ml flask.
- 2) 5 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid H₂SO₄ was added to the sample and left for 24 hours.
- 3) The samples were heated at 400°C for half an hour.
- 4) 3 ml of concentrated acid mixture (perchloric acid 4% + sulfuric acid 96%) was added and heated until the solution becomes clear; distilled water must be added to the solution to make total volume of 50 ml.
- 5) The total nitrogen was estimated by distillation process using Kjeldabl method according to the method (Page et al., 1982).

$$\% \text{ Protein} = \% \text{ nitrogen} \times 6.25 \quad \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Determination of the total soluble carbohydrates in the Jujube leaves (mg/100gm)

The total soluble carbohydrate content of leaves of infested and non-infested Jujube cultivars was estimated by phenol method with concentrated sulfuric acid H₂SO₄(Dubois et al., 1956); 0.5 gm of dried and ground sample was taken and placed in a 100-ml flask; 70 ml of distilled water was added to sample, and was heated in a water bath at boiling degree for one hour; the solution was left for one h at room temperature, then the solution was filtered using filter paper; 25 ml of distilled water was added to 5 ml of the solution. 1 ml of final solution was added to 1 ml of phenol and 5 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid H₂SO₄. The absorbance was estimated using Spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 490 nm; the amount of total soluble carbohydrates was estimated using the standard glucose curve.

Determination of chlorophyll pigment in the Jujube leaves

The total chlorophyll dye was estimated in the leaves of infested and non-infested Jujube cultivars according to the method of Goodwin (1976)(Goodwin, 1976); 0.5 gm from each sample was taken; 10 ml of 80% acetone was added to the sample; the sample was crushed by using a ceramic mortar; the samples were centrifuged at a rate of 160 cycles/min for 10 minutes, filtered, and completed the volume to 20 ml of acetone. A Spectrophotometer was used to measure the absorbance of the dye at the wavelengths 663 and 645 nm. The amount of dye was calculated in the form of mg / liter according to the following equation:

$$\text{Total chlorophyll mg/L} = [(20.2 * \text{O.D } 645) + (8.02 * \text{O.D } 663)] \quad \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

The absorbance measured at a wavelength of 645 nm = O.D 645

The absorbance measured at a wavelength of 663 nm = O.D 663

Determination of phenols of Jujube leaves

The phenols were estimated in the leaves of infested and non-infested Jujube cultivars according to the method of Waterhouse (2001)(Waterhouse, 2001). 2.5 gm of dry sample was taken; 200 ml of distilled water was added to the sample; the mixture was placed in a water bath at degree boiling for one hour and left for the next day; the mixture was filtered; 1 ml of the filtrate was added to it 1.5 ml of the 10% diluted Follen reagent and left for 5 minutes; the solution was mixed with 1.5 ml of anhydrous sodium carbonate solution 6% NaCo₃ and left for 40 minutes at room temperature. The absorbance was estimated by using a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 725 nm after the device was reset 1 ml distilled water + 1.5 ml Follen reagent + 1.5 NaCo₃).

Statistical analysis

The data were tested using analysis of variance (ANOVA) and means were compared using a Least Significant Difference (LSD) test at $P \leq 0.05$. Correlation analysis involved measuring two the variables of infestation rates and the chemical analysis of Jujube cultivars, and assessing the relationship between them.

RESULTS

Infestation rates of flat-headed borers on different cultivars of Jujube trees.

The results of Table (1) showed that there were significant differences in the percentage of infestation with flat-headed borers *C. affines* on the different Jujube cultivars in Basra Province during the growing season of 2021/2022. The highest infestation rates of the borers were 42.17 and 40.77%, in Zubair and Safwan regions respectively; while the lowest infestation were 9.40 and 11.29%, at Madinah and Imam Al-Sadiq regions, respectively. The results also indicated that the highest infestation of flat-headed borers was on the cv. Tuffahi in Basra Province, with an average rate of 61.06%, followed the Bambawi and Ziatooni cultivars, reaching 18.51 and 18.45%, respectively. While, the lowest infestation was 9.95% on cultivar Wild.

The results of the statistical analysis showed the highest percentage of infestation was recorded on cv. Tuffahi in the Safwan and Shatt Al-Arab regions, reaching 88.89 and 84.35%, respectively; whereas, the lowest infestation was recorded on the cv. Wild at Al-Madina and Imam Al-Sadiq regions, where the percentage of infestation of 0.76 and 1.13%, respectively.

Table (1) Infestation rates of flat-headed borers on some Jujube cultivars at different regions of Basra Province during the growing season 2021/2022.

regions	Infestation rates% of flat-headed borers on some cultivars				mean
	Wild	Ziatooni	Tuffahi	Bambawi	
Al-Mdaina	0.76	5.72	23.06	8.07	9.40
Al-Sadeq	1.13	4.77	32.03	7.24	11.29
Al-Qurna	2.41	12.03	35.19	12.73	15.59
Al-Deer	2.76	11.32	55.63	14.41	21.03
Al-Hartha	6.05	24.22	65.33	15.92	27.88
Al-Nashwa	4.91	21.81	65.28	12.49	26.12
Shat Al-arab	11.17	32.02	84.35	26.67	38.55

Abu-Al-khaseb	15.30	18.09	83.82	31.21	37.11
Al-Zuber	28.88	29.91	77.00	32.87	42.17
Safwan	26.10	24.56	88.89	23.51	40.77
Mean	9.95	18.45	61.06	18.51	26.99
L.S.D.	1.98				3.14

L.S.D. of interaction= 6.28

Biochemical traits for Plant Defense

Phenols of the trunk phloem

The results of the chemical analysis of the stems of different Jujube cultivars (Table 2) indicated the presence of multiple phenolic compounds in the phloem trunk of Jujube trees. There were 15 phenolic compounds, which varied in their concentrations in the cultivars; 4hydroxy had the highest concentration in the phloem trunk of cv. Bembawi with a concentration of 912.00 ppm; while, Pyrogallol had the lowest concentration in cv. Tuffahi, which reached 0.02 ppm. The results indicated that Bembawi was characterized by a high concentration of total phenols, reaching 2320.00 ppm; however, the cultivar Wild had lowest concentration of total phenols, which averaged 859.00 ppm.

In general, cv. Tuffahi was distinguished by its low concentrations of rutin, gallic and caffeic compounds, while some phenolic compounds were found in this cultivar in high concentrations such as Chloroge, Nigellore, Lignan and Eugenol; compared to cv. Wild variety which possessed high concentrations of the first group and low concentrations of the second group of the above phenolic compounds.

The study of the correlation relationship (Table No. 3) indicated that there was a negative correlation between the infestation of flat-headed borers on the studied Jujube cultivars and the concentrations of phenolic acids in those cultivars; the highest values of the correlation coefficient (r) were -0.97 and -0.93 for rutin and gallic acids, respectively); the increase in the concentrations of these acids was accompanied by a decrease in the rate of insect infestation on the cultivars. While the phenolic acids Eugenol, Chloroge, Nigellore, quercetin and Lignan recorded the highest values of the positive correlation (0.91, 0.76, 0.77, 0.59 and 0.45).

Table (2) Phenolic compounds in Phenols of the trunk phloem of some Jujube cultivars.

phenolic	Concentration Phenolic compounds (ppm) of the trunk phloem					L.S.D.(0.01)
	Wild	Ziatooni	Tuffahi	Bambawi	Mean	
pyrogallol	0.094	0.224	0.028	0.390	0.184	0.1865
Gallic	0.123	0.077	0.032	0.091	0.081	0.1565
Rutin	1.80	2.00	0.03	1.85	1.42	2.123
Kaempfe	0.294	0.714	0.475	1.484	0.742	0.4082
Vanillic	128.00	323.00	95.00	405.00	238.00	229.0
Caffeic	1.30	33.10	9.20	24.30	17.00	24.75
Cinnamic	9.30	29.00	21.50	106.8	41.60	35.57

Catechol	34.00	115.00	185.00	491.00	206.00	NS
4hydroxy	436.00	320.00	482.00	912.00	537.00	NS
qurcitin	7.50	9.50	36.60	39.50	23.30	NS
Cinnamalde	26.00	60.00	55.00	293.00	108.00	130.7
Chloroge	194.00	43.00	343.00	28.00	152.00	192.5
Nigllore	17.40	4.10	30.00	5.60	14.30	12.02
Lignan	2.456	4.657	4.099	1.395	3.152	0.8137
Eugenol	4.80	7.90	28.10	9.90	12.70	35.32
Totel	859.00	949.00	1290.00	2320.00	1354.00	1141.0

Table (3) Correlation relationship between the infestation rates of flat-headed borers and Phenols of the trunk phloem of some Jujube cultivars

Phenols compounds	Correlation coefficient
Pyrogallol	-0.53
Gallic	-0.93
Rutin	-0.97
Kaempfe	-0.13
Vanillic	-0.49
Caffic	-0.20
Cinnamic	-0.19
Catechol	0.04
4hydroxy	-0.08
Cinnamalde	-0.18
Qurcitin	0.59
Chloroge	0.76
Nigellore	0.77
Lignin	0.45
Eugenol	0.91

The Moisture content of branches

The results of the statistical analysis in Table 4 showed that there were significant differences between the percentage of moisture and the infestation in the branches of trees; it was noticed that the one-year-old branches (moisture= 52.59%) are usually not infested with the borers *C. affinis*, compared to the two years or more branches (moisture= 30.90%), which are attacked by the pest. The study also indicates that the apple cultivar has the most moisture cultivars in the branches of the trees, with an average of 44.44%.

The study confirmed that the moisture in the branches of trees had an effect on the infestation of the flat-headed borer *C. affinis*. An inverse correlation was recorded between the infestation rate on the studied Jujube cultivars and the moisture content in the cultivars branches (correlation coefficient $r = - 0.15$); these results may explain the lack of the flat-headed borer injury to the new twigs compared to old branches.

Table (4) Moisture content of the one and two years branches of some Jujube cultivars.

Cultivars	% moisture content of branches (Year)		Mean
	year	Two or more	
bathry	48.30	38.81	43.55
zaitony	53.57	32.27	42.92
Tufahy	58.11	30.78	44.44
bambawii	50.40	21.75	36.08
Rate moisture	52.59	30.90	41.75
L.S.D.	5.70		8.06

L.S.D. = 11.40

Chemical responses of Jujube cultivars to flat-headed borer's infestation

The results of Table 5 showed that there were significant differences among the protein percentage in the leaves of the infested and un-infested Jujube cultivars; the average percentage of protein in the healthy leaves was 18.92%, however, the rates of the leaves protein were decreased in infested trees, with average of 15.09%. The study also showed the percentage of protein varied in healthy leaves, with averages of 20.41, 19.83, 18.22 and 17.20% in cv.s Tuffahi, Bambawi, Zaitooni and Wild, respectively; however, the infestation of flat-headed borers led to decrease in the rates of protein, which were 15.31, 15.31, 15.16 and 14.58% in the leaves of the above infested cultivars, respectively.

The results of Table 6 indicated the total carbohydrate content estimated of 86.19, 74.09, 65.50 and 61.33% in healthy leaves of Tuffahi, Bambawi, Wild and Zaitooni, respectively. However, it was observed that these percentages decreased to 64.31, 61.60, 55.21 and 52.16% in the leaves of the infested trees with flat-headed borers on the above cultivars, respectively.

Table (5) The effect of infestation of flat-headed borers on the percentage of protein in the leaves of some Jujube cultivars

Cultivars	% protein in the leaves of Jujube trees		Mean
	Non-infested	infested	
Wild	17.20	14.58	15.89
Ziatooni	18.22	15.16	16.69
Tuffahi	20.41	15.31	17.86
Bambawii	19.83	15.31	17.57
Mean	18.92	15.09	17.00

L.S.D.	1.52	1.07
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L.S.D. = 2.15

Table (6) The effect of infestation of flat-headed borer on the percentage of carbohydrates in the leaves of some Jujube cultivars.

Cultivars	% carbohydrates in the leaves of trees		Mean
	Non-infested	infested	
Wild	65.50	55.21	60.36
Ziatooni	61.33	52.16	56.75
Tuffahi	86.19	64.31	75.25
Bambawii	74.09	61.60	67.85
Mean	71.78	58.32	65.05
L.S.D.	5.74		8.12

L.S.D. = 11.49

The infestation of flat-headed borer also affected the leaf chlorophyll content. The results of the statistical analysis in Table 7 showed that there were significant differences in the content of chlorophyll pigment of the leaves of the healthy and infested trees; in general, the average of chlorophyll content was 4.22 mg/ 100 gm of the leaves of the healthy trees, compared to that of the infested trees' cultivars, with average of 1.82 mg / 100 gm. At each cultivar, the chlorophyll content of the leaves varied in the healthy jujube cultivars; they recorded 4.90, 4.02, 3.92 and 3.28 mg/ 100 gm of leaves of Wild, Tuffahi, Bambawi and Zatooni, which decreased to 1.59 And 1.98, 1.92 and 1.82 mg / 100 gm in the leaves of the infested Jujube cultivars, respectively.

Table (7) The effect of infestation of flat-headed borers on the amount of chlorophyll in the leaves of some Jujube cultivars.

Cultivars	chlorophyll in the leaves ml/ 100g		Mean
	Non-infested	infested	
Wild	4.90	1.59	3.24
Ziatooni	3.28	1.82	2.18
Tuffahi	4.02	1.98	2.49
Bambawii	3.92	1.92	2.92
Mean	4.22	1.82	2.78
L.S.D.	0.98		1.38

L.S.D. = 1.70

The results of response of the resistance of Jujube trees to infestation of the flat-headed stem borer (Table 8) showed that there were significant differences in the percentage of phenols of the leaves in the healthy and infested trees. In general, the concentration of phenols in the infested trees increased, reaching 9.781%, compared to that of the non-infested trees, reaching of 9.455%. The

rate of phenols was 9.505, 9.466, 9.466 and 9.382% in the leaves of non-infested cv.s Bambawi, Tuffahi, Wild and Zatooni; The rates increased as a result of the infestation by borers to 9.724, 9.805 and 9.733 and 9.861% in the leaves of the above infested cultivars, respectively.

Table (8) The effect of infestation of flat-headed borers on the percentage of phenols in the leaves of some Jujube cultivars.

Cultivars	% phenols in the leaves		Mean
	Non-infested	infested	
Wild	9.46	9.73	9.60
Ziatooni	9.38	9.86	9.62
Tuffahi	9.46	9.80	9.63
Bambawii	9.50	9.72	9.61
Mean	9.45	9.78	9.61
L.S.D.	0.09		0.13

L.S.D. = 0.19

DISCUSSION

Flat-headed borers (Buprestidae) are economically important pest causes damage to many trees species globally; for example, *Agilus planipennis* which has killed thousands of ash trees in Detroit, Michigan, since 2002 (Cappaert et al., 2005) is one of the most destructive and costly invasive forest insects (Aukema et al., 2011). The results of this study showed that the infestation of flat-headed borers *C. affines* spread on Jujube orchards throughout Basra Province; the infestation of the borer *C. affines* led to significant economic damage Jujube fruit production in the case of severe injury (Adkins et al., 2010); the highest rates of infestation were recorded in southern and western regions of Basra. (Abu al-Khasib, Safwan and al-Zubayr) compared to northern Basra (Madina and Imam Al-Sadiq); this may be due to the different environmental conditions of Basra regions, which vary between the desert environment in the west of the province compared to other areas of the sedimentary plain environment in southern Iraq (Alyousuf and Nikpay, 2020). The infestation varied between the Jujube cultivars plantation of Basra province; the highest rate of infestation of flat-headed borers recoded on cv. Tuffahi, followed by the Zatooni and Bambawi, while the lowest rate was found on cv. Wild; that may be attributed to of variation of jujube fruit quantity and quality; thus the borers preference varied according to chemical and physical characteristics of the cultivars (Al-Zubaidi, 1992.) (Alyousuf et al., 2004). The extensive plantation of Jujube trees cv. Tuffahi in Basra Province may be one of the reasons behind of the invasion of the borers; widespread plantation could be attributed to the commercial and marketing value and consumer desire which encourage the growers to grow more tree annually.

The recent infestation of flat-headed borers *C. affines* on jujube plantation previously not recorded has increased interest in understanding how Jujube cultivars respond to an unexpected borers attack. This study indicated to the presence of different phenolic compounds in the phloem trunk of Jujube trees. There were 15 phenolic compounds, which varied in their concentrations in the cultivars. Phenolic compounds (phenols, alcohols, phenolic acids, phenylpropanoids,

coumarins, flavonoids, and tannins) are among the important plant secondary metabolites, which found in all higher plants (Eleftherianos et al., 2006); they act as plant inhibitors of insect enzymes (Leszczyński, 2001); as well as their inhibition of digestion in insects, including beetles, thus reducing the availability of food, which absorbed in the alimentary canal, by reducing the permeability of the midgut to digested nutrients, (Czerniewicz et al., 2017). Insects are characterized by the alkalinity of the stomach, which enhances the oxidation of phenols as they move through the alimentary canal. The oxidation of phenols creates oxidative stress in the insect, which affects the growth of the insect (Sohal and Sharma, 2011).

The results of this study indicated that the phenolic compounds (rutin, gallic and caffeic) were found in low concentrations in susceptible cv. Tuffahi; however, the high concentrations of the same above phenols was recorded in cv. Wild, which is a resistant cultivar; thus Tuffahi was characterized as a susceptible cultivar due to the high borers infestation and the low concentration of above phenols.

Rutin and quercetin are among the flavonoid compounds that affect the insects and plants interaction; they are categorized among the basic and induced plant resistance mechanisms (Singh et al., 2021, Simmonds, 2001) through their effect on insect behavior; Rutin may adversely affect the probing behavior of proboscis penetration of aphid, *Myzus persicae*, feeding on the phloem tissue of *Brassica rapa* ssp. *pekinensis*, while the increased concentration of quercetin promoted penetration of the proboscis of *Acyrtosiphon pisum* into the phloem and other tissues of *Pisum sativum* (Stec et al., 2021).

Gallic acid (3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoic acid) is an important compound found in a variety of plants; it is produced by the metabolic pathway of shikimate acid (Ananthakrishnan, 1997), which affects the development of some insect pests; It was found that Gallic acid has the ability to disrupt the development of *Bactrocera cucurbitae* (Coquillett) (Diptera: Tephritidae); this phenolic compound may cause oxidative stress in the insect body (Sharma and Sohal, 2013). The midgut of herbivore is a highly oxidative environment, as phenolic compounds when ingested by insects would be oxidized in the insect gut lumen, affecting essential nutrients and midgut tissues (Barbehenn et al., 2005). The compound gallic acid in the bark and leaf extracts of *Triadica sebifera* was also found to have an effective effect by inhibiting the AChE enzyme in the aphid *Aphis craccivora* Koch (Hemiptera: Aphididae), which infesting leguminous crops and also transmits plant viruses (Dolma et al., 2022). It also had a lethal effect against *Spodoptera litura* larvae and delayed larval development (Punia et al., 2021). Also, the external application of gallic acid induced the direct defense of the tea plant (*Camellia sinensis*) against engineered tea larvae (*Ectropis obliqua*), by activating the signals of Jasmonic Acid; that led to the induction of the production of anti-nutrition compounds to insects and thus developing the resistance to the insect (Zhang et al., 2022). Usually, cultivars of trees with low concentrations of phenolic compounds such as gallic acid and Caffeic acid are more sensitive to pest infestation (Gantner et al., 2019).

High concentrations of other phenolic compounds were found in the Tuffahi cultivar compared to the rest of the cultivars, such as Chlorogenic, Lignin and Eugenol compounds. These compounds are known for their prominent role in pest resistance. Chlorogenic acid is one of the

most abundant types of beneficial polyphenols in plants; it has a role as a nutritional antioxidant in plant foods. Also, it has been shown to be an effective defense against a wide range of herbivorous insects (Leiss et al., 2009, Kundu and Vadassery, 2019). Lignin, as a phenolic compound, plays an important role in the defense of plants against insects; it acts as a feeding inhibitor, as well as its effect on specific physiological functions of insects (Harmatha and Dinan, 2003, Wang et al., 2020). Eugenol also has an important role in insect resistance as anti-acetylcholinesterase, larvicide, and anti-feed, as well as its toxicity against many insects, including *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Vargas-Méndez et al., 2019, Fernandes et al., 2020), *Aedes aegypti* (Adhikari et al., 2022) and *Sitophilus zeamais* Motschulsky (Coleoptera: curculionidae) (Prates et al., 2019); the anti-nutritional activity of eight Eugenol derivatives from thyme was tested. *Thymus vulgaris* Linnaeus (Lamiaceae) and *Syzygium aromaticum* Linnaeus (Myrtaceae) were tested against fourth instar larvae of red palm weevil *Rhynchophorus ferrugineus* as an anti-feeding agent (Yan et al., 2021).

Despite the high concentrations of the compounds Chloroge, Lignans and Eugenol in cv. Tuffahi, the insect infestation on this cultivar was higher compared to the rest of the cultivars; insects are known to possess detoxification enzymes such as GST, cytochrome P450 monooxygenases and carboxyl / cholinesterase; these mechanisms are responsible for helping plant-feeding insects to maintain their physiological development By detoxing the xenobiotic substances, including pesticides and toxic secondary metabolites of the host plants (Oakshott et al., 2010).

The study indicated that the infestation of borers were affected by the moisture content of the trunks and branches of the jujube trees; No injury occurs in the one year branches due the high level of moisture content; (Beddes, 2014), showed in his study that there are a group of factors that affect the infestation of flat-headed stem borers; some factors increase the infestations, including drought, stress and wounds on trees. Trees and all these factors affect the moisture content and lead to its decrease, thus making the plant ready for injury.

(Knof, 1972) indicated that the cause of injury to the fruit trees in Iraq with the fruit borers is due to the lack of irrigation; (Al-Mayah and Al-Eidani, 1992) mentioned that the weakness of the trees due to the lack of irrigation leads to injury by borers as a result of the low moisture in the plants. The study showed that the infestation of Jujube trees by flat-headed borers led to a decrease in the percentage of protein, carbohydrates and chlorophyll in the leaves of all the infested cultivars in this study. Attacking the phloem of the trees disrupt the flow of important nutrients to the other parts of the infested tree; that leads to affect the protein synthesis in the plant (Hansen et al., 2012, Hansen et al., 2011).

The study showed an increase in the concentration of phenols in the leaves of Jujube cultivars after infesting by borers; this is consistent with what was mentioned by (Usha Rani and Jyothsna, 2010) who showed that phenols have a significant role and an effective contribution against pests; usually the infested plants by pests recorded a significant increase in the percentage of phenols compared to plants that were not exposed to the infestation. (Jander et al., 2001) showed that phenolic compounds have an important and effective role against pests that infect plants; the phenolic

concentration increases and accumulates in large quantities in infested plants, which leads to a defect in the physiological processes of the pests. Finally, plants have a set of integrated defense systems against pests that attack the bark and wood; the mechanical defenses provide hardness or the thickness of the tissues that prevents insect borers attacks (Fäldt et al., 2003). Phenols are among the phytochemical defenses, which provide plant protection against a wide range of (Martin et al., 2002, Christiansen et al., 1999).

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

"The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare".

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